

Stress Levels and Perceived Self-Efficacy of Teachers Handling Inclusive Education

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ABSTRACT

This study pursued to assess the stress levels and perceived self-efficacy of teachers handling inclusive education. It utilized a descriptive comparative method and it was limited to 40 teachers-respondents. Standardized and researcher-made instruments and appropriate statistical tools were utilized to determine their level of stress and perceived self-efficacy. The respondents were classified according to the following profiles: Age, Sex, Civil Status, Educational Attainment, Job Rank, Work Shift, Number of Seminars and Trainings Attended, Length of Service and Number of Learners with Special Educational Needs, from which the researcher measured the related levels of stress and perceived self-efficacy. Of the 40 respondents, 16 or 40% are from the 26-30 years old age bracket, 11 or 27% are between 36 to 40 years old, 8 or 20% are 20-25 years old, 4 or 10% are 31-35 years old, and 1 or 3% is between 41-45 years old. Majority of the participants are female, with a number of 25 or 62.5% compared to the male respondents, which accounts for the remaining 15 or 37.5%. 22 or 55% of the participants are married, while 18 or 45% are single. Meanwhile, 25 respondents, or 62.5% have earned MA/MS units, 12 or 30% have BA/BS degrees, 2 or 5% have earned their MA degrees and 1 or 2.5% have PhD/EdD units. Rank-wise, 32 respondents or 80% are Teacher 1, 5 or 12.5% are Teacher 2 and 3 or 7.5% are Teacher 3. 30 or 75% belong to the AM shift, while 10 or 25% are from the PM shift. Majority of the respondents have not attended any training; 23 or 57.5% did not have any supplemental training to date, while the remaining 17 or 42.5% have attended at least 1-3 trainings. In terms of length of service, 18 or 45% are relatively new, 14 or 35% have served for 6-10 years, 6 or 15% have been working for 11-15 years and 2 or 5% are with the school for 16-20 years. Lastly, 38 or 95% have 1-5 learners with special educational needs and 2 or 5% have 6-10 learners with similar requirements. From these data, the absolute value of the Pearson r value was computed and determined to be equivalent to 0.493, greater than or equal to 0.4 and less than or equal to 0.6; This indicated that stress level and perceived self-efficacy has moderately strong negative correlation.

Although the respondents are likely to experience stress, the study revealed that the male participants are more likely to be stressed as compared to their female counterparts. Also, those with lower educational attainment and higher job rank are just as likely to be stressed. The study also revealed that the older participants appear to have lower self-efficacy. The researcher proposes an alternative program be adapted in the school to manage stress and help promote self-efficacy. Also, additional studies may be conducted to refine findings gathered.

Key words: Inclusive Education, Stress, Self-efficacy.

INTRODUCTION

The Philippine Government, through the Presidential Decree No. 603, has established a decree concerning the needs for the Persons with Disabilities which aims to strengthen the quality of education for all regardless of their conditions. Though it had sought diversity to all, the question lies on the capacity and preparedness of the academe sector.

Herein, according to the seminar that the researcher attended in Baguio City on “The Changing Landscape of Special Education Worldwide: Its Impact on the Current Practices in the K to 12,” the lecturer mentioned that the practice of Special Education catering for children with disabilities is indeed challenging; hence, as teachers, caregivers, and educators involved in education delivery services for children with disabilities, they need to be constantly sensitive and productive towards the current global settings and development on trend, practices and educational agenda towards providing special education services for children with disabilities. She emphasized that the current education agenda is to deliver and provide educational settings that is holistic and from early childhood to youth and adulthood emphasizing on the acquisition of

skills for work, underlining the importance of citizenship in the plural and independent work where the education focuses on inclusion, equity and gender equality.

Accordingly, Dr. Hussain (2016) Deputy Director Special Education Department Ministry of Education – Malaysia added, that there are five aspects that are important to be addressed in this current education setting for children with disabilities. (1) The Wellness of Being of Children with Disabilities, which emphasizes that the state of wellness especially for children with special needs is very pertinent to encourage healthy growth of the children's mental, physical, emotion and overall well-being. In this case, for a child with disability to function and live a meaningful life the wellness aspects of the child must be given priority. (2) Independence of Life Skills. In this aspect, according to Brolin, students with disabilities would need to master skills that are crucial for them to engage in meaningful employment as well as preparing them for independent living; the skills are: managing personal finances, selecting and managing household, caring for personal needs, safety awareness, preparing and consuming food, buying and caring for clothing, exhibiting responsible citizenship, using recreational facilities and engaging in leisure activities and getting around.

Hence, as educators, managing and educating children with special needs do not only develop the cognitive skills but they also equally develop the children's abilities to manage to lead independence lives in a dignified manner and opportunity. (3) Inclusive Education – this means that the current educational setting is toward inclusivity in order to provide educational experience and growth for children with disabilities. In this case, teachers and educator in the regular setting and in special education setting have to change their ways of thinking, interventions and educational approach to teaching and educating children with disabilities in setting whereby diversity and differences are respected and accepted. (4) Disability awareness – it emphasizes that in any inclusive setting, disability awareness is very fundamental awareness that has to be disseminated, instilled and inculcated at levels in the society. For educators, fostering a positive attitude towards disability is very important as teachers are role models for their children. And (5) Technical and Vocational Education (TVET), which is an educational process involving, in addition to general education, the study of technologies and relayed sciences and acquisition of practical skills, etc. By opening training centers and emphasizing on TVET policies and programs, the negative perceptions on disabled employee can be reduced and thus increased the opportunity for disabled people to secure a job or career that can lead to attainment and self-respect.

According to Dr. Hussain, special education teachers need to keep abreast with the latest development and current trends. Teachers training especially for pre-service and in service teachers must be sensitive and should respond to the current changes so as to ensure that teachers are well informed and well-equipped the necessary skills and information to deliver meaningful education services.

The current set up of the Special Education (SPED) in the country is that the curriculum is being taught to all to a diverse set of students to integrate the same accessibility in the education from both regular students and those with special needs.

It is a challenging step for the local and the international academe sector and must be equipped with the current trend, practices, and changing needs of the individuals that will create more sensible teachings styles. Moreover, creating a holistic environment is also a challenge to the educators; hence it is important that the welfare of the students is being taken care of, they must enable to learn how to be independent in their life skills, and they must grow as an individual without barriers in their way of thinking that will enhance their acceptability in the society.

However, despite of the established decree concerning the needs for persons with disabilities and the legal mandates for inclusive education there are still other academe sectors do not uphold the said order. Administrator and general education teachers are still not aware and do not accept the inclusive education that would somehow lead to stressful situation on the part of the general education teacher aside from the fact that most of them are not sped teacher by profession.

According to (Tugrul&Celik 2002,) Even though the teachers' professional competency contributes a lot to their effectiveness, the role of psychological well-being in terms of teacher effectiveness cannot be denied. One of the important indicators of teacher's psychological well-being in school-settings is the degree of stress. When the literature about job stress is reviewed, it can be determined that there has been a growing interest about job stress experienced by the teachers. This state has led the researcher to conduct studies to discern variables related with this condition to understand the problem more deeply.

Adams (1999) emphasized that all people experience stressful events at one time in their lives, because stress is decisive to human life. According to Kaizer and Polezynski (1982) and Terry (1997) stresses have been realized as the reaction of the body of every person to physical and psychological factors which impact on that person.

It is characterized by the exhaustion of employees' emotional resources, negative attitudes towards service recipients and decrease in the feeling of personal accomplishment (Maslach & Jackson 1981). Accordingly, job stress consists of dimensions, namely low energy, fatigue and emotional worn out.

Hence in order to cope with this situation, the employees feel alienated to their job mentally and emotionally. Moreover, job stress has a relation to psychological symptoms like tension, neuroticism, addiction and depression.

Kokkinos, (2007) appealed that one of the leading such sectors is education, in which there is an intense teacher-student interaction.

International Labour Organisation also defined Stress as the adverse reaction people have to excessive pressure and demands placed upon them. The nature of work is changing at a rapid promptness. Possibly even before, job stress bearings a threat to the health of workers and in turn to the continued existence of the organization and ultimately the prosperity of a nation.

Section 5 of the Occupational Safety and Health Act 2005 (OSHA) clearly stipulates that "Every employer shall, so far as is reasonably practicable, ensure the safety, health and welfare at work of his employees." Occupational Health is the promotion and maintenance of the highest degree of physical, mental and social wellbeing of workers in all occupations (International Labour Organisation).

Although it is not possible to give a universal prescription for preventing stress at work, it is possible to offer guidelines on stress prevention and management to assist employers and employees. The guidelines provide simple, concise and systematic steps that can be followed by an employer or an employee to better manage stress and prevent injuries and ill health at work.

An important concept related with job stress is self-efficacy. Balci, (2005) defined Efficacy as the necessary knowledge, skills and attitudes to carry out role or to behave in an expected manner.

The concept of self-efficacy, according to Albert Bandura is related to the self-perception of one's own competencies. He detailed that self-efficacy has an important place in Social Learning Theory. Accordingly, self-efficacy is the belief of having the capacity to perform the expected tasks efficiently by organizing and carrying out the necessary activities.

Tuckman, (1991) also defined self-efficacy is ones beliefs that she can overcome a situation or problem and has the ability to fulfil a particular task.

Tschannen Moral et. al (1998) cited that the quality of education will be achieved through the self- efficacy of teachers. He defined teacher's self-efficacy as the teacher's belief in his or her capability to organize and execute courses of action. Teacher will be able to contribute their best if they have this kind of traits.

Since education is an applied field of science, it is necessary to seek solution for the education and the entire education system. The solution of the problem in the education system depends on the development of the modern curricula and the self-efficacy of teachers who are handling students with special needs.

This study aims to determine the level of stress and a teachers' perceived self-efficacy of teachers handling inclusive education through the collection of quantitative data from a convenient sample of secondary school teachers of Bagong Nayon II National High School.

Background of the Study

This study aims to determine the level of stress and perceived self-efficacy of teachers handling inclusive education through the collection of quantitative data from a convenient sample of secondary school teachers of Bagong Nayon II National High School.

The researcher would like to identify the level of stress and perceived self-efficacy of teachers who are handling students with special educational needs. The suggestions of the findings of the study will help to reduce and diminish the level of stress and the possible ways to increase teachers' self-efficacy in handling students with special educational needs.

Special education program of Bagong Nayon II National High School is currently catering 21 learners with different exceptionalities; mild Autism, cerebral palsy, learning disability, visual impairment, hearing impairment, speech impairment and intellectual disability. Most of the students in special education program have undergone mainstreaming to regular classroom setting with the teacher.

The substantial challenges that may impede successful implementing of inclusive education includes lack of knowledge and skills on Inclusive Education, lack of facilities, lack of awareness among all stakeholders, curriculum difficulties and time restrictions educations. To completely engage and shows improvement in the general classroom, learners need more to be actively present in the school.

Their main necessity is to get involved in group and individual instruction, provide educational settings that is holistic and from early childhood to youth and adulthood emphasizing on the acquisition of skills for work. As far as teachers' self-efficacy is concern, general education teachers must have this characteristic in order to have successful inclusive education. (Macbeath et al, 2016) stated that appropriate adjustments must be made so that children with special educational needs can genuinely participate in the learning activities that happen in the school.

Inclusive Education

Inclusive Education is defined as the practice of educating most children in the same classroom, including children with intellectual, emotional, or physical disabilities. There were two concepts of inclusion apply first is the placement concept second is learning concept. According to Anderson, Klassen & Georgiou, (2007) mainstreaming or integration, places children with mild or moderate disabilities in the same educational setting as typically developing children in the hope that all children would benefit from the experience In the US, this mainstream placement includes also children with more severe disabilities. In the placement concept, students "can be in but not of the class in terms of social and learning membership" Ferguson, (2008). Inclusion however, has shifted toward a greater emphasis on the quality of learning. The learning concept is the extent to which a school or community welcomes students with disabilities as full members of the group and values their contributions Anderson et al., (2007).

Warnock (2005) also mentioned that it includes all children wherever they learn best. This may mean pull- out system with individualized instruction in the mainstream setting or the provision of a teacher-aide in the classroom to accommodate special learning needs.

The main aim of the inclusion of special needs students into mainstream educational settings was equality of access and opportunities for these students however is there a price on this equality? Idol (2006) states that the educators, both elementary and secondary are very much in favor of inclusion based on what they perceived are the benefits of this integration for these students. However, in order for the students with special education needs to gain by enrolling in mainstream education the additional tools and resources they require as a result of their disability needs to be present and available to meet their needs.

In a study by Hewitt-Taylor, (2009) The inclusion effort requires efficient coordination of services, delegation and ownership of responsibilities, pre- agreed allocated funding and sufficient support and training for staff in order to meet the needs of special needs students. Their study also found that teachers asked to develop new practices and policies in order to include special needs students in the class hence resulting in an increased workload for the teacher.

This study would suggest that as a result of inclusion of special needs students into mainstream education there has been an increase in teacher workload and demands, hence inadvertently an increase in stress for the teachers.

As cited by Webster (2014) there are generally two models for inclusion: Push in and fullinclusion. Push in has the special education teacher enter the classroom to provide instruction and support to children. The push in teacher will bring materials into the classroom. The teacher may work with the child on math during math period, or perhaps reading during the literacy block. The push in teacher also often provides instructional support to the general education teacher. Full inclusion places a special education teacher as a full partner in a classroom with a general education teacher. The general education teacher is the teacher of record, and is responsible for the child, even though the child may have an Individual Educational Plan (IEP).

Implementing the policies of Inclusive Education is one of the goals that was promoted in the Philippines long time ago but achieving this goal seems very challenging; particularly inclusion of disabled children in mainstream primary schools (Miles & Farhad, 1999; UNICEF, 2003, Haider, 2008). Under Public Law 94-142 (Education of All Handicapped Children Act, 1975) altered the face of education and set the stage for inclusive education and the UNESCO (1994) stated that

“Schools should accommodate all children regardless of their physical, intellectual, emotional, social, linguistic or other conditions. Inclusive education is commonly associated with the education of children with disabilities or special educational needs in mainstream schools (Cummings, Dyson & Millward, 2003).

Mukhopadhyay (2009) says that “the fundamental principle of the inclusive school is that all children should learn together, wherever possible, regardless of any difficulties or differences, they may have”. There are severity of their disability but inclusive education is” Education for all” respecting the rights of every human being according to his/her needs. It requires commitment, tolerance, patience and love of a person who carry out inclusive education program.

The Education for All (EFA) initiative, first put forth in 1990 by the international community, marked a global movement towards providing quality basic education to all children, youth and adults, United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), (1990). In order to comply with the Act and educate all learners, schools were and are still required to merge general and special education into a single delivery system, Matlock, Fiedler, & Walsh, (2001).

According to UNESCO (2003) Inclusive Education (IE) is an approach or a process which occurs when children with and without disabilities, HIV status, age and children of diverse backgrounds and abilities learn together in the same classroom, interact socially with each other within the regular school setting for the whole day. Inclusive education means welcoming all children, without discrimination into regular or general schools. It calls for a respect of difference and celebration of diversity.

Diversity helps students at risk to overcome the risk of failure and negative perception about the other people through involvement in a thoughtful and caring community of learners. Each student has unique contribution to offer to other learners. Each student has strengths and needs. They have their own ability and a skill that need to be enhanced by the help of their teachers.

In a journal article entitled Toolkit on Disability for Africa Inclusive education, as defined in the Salamanca Statement involves gratitude of the need to work towards “schools for all institutions which include everybody, celebrate differences, support learning, and respond to individual needs.” Inclusion in the context of education is based on the idea that all children should learn together, regardless of differences or disability. Inclusive education begins with the premise that all learners have unique characteristics, interests, abilities and particular learning needs and, further, that learners with special education needs must have equal access to and receive individual accommodation in the general education system. Inclusive education approaches differences and diversity affirmatively, recognizing the value of such differences and the learning opportunities that such diversity offers.

Inclusion denotes transition from separate, segregated learning environments for persons with disabilities reflected in the “special education” approach, to schooling in the general education system. Effective transitions from special education approaches to inclusive education requires careful planning and structural changes to ensure that learners with disabilities are not placed within the regular or mainstream school system without the appropriate accommodation and supports that ensure an inclusive learning environment. It is now assumed that inclusive education benefits communities, families, teachers, and students by ensuring that children with disabilities attend school with their peers and providing them with adequate support to succeed both academically and socially. It is also agreed that communities benefit from inclusion because the introduction of children with disabilities into mainstream schools introduces children with disabilities into local communities and neighborhoods and helps break down barriers and prejudice. Communities become more accepting of difference, and everyone benefits from a friendlier, open environment. Lastly, maintaining separate schooling for children with disabilities is not cost-effective or sustainable over the long term; all too frequently exclusion leads to inferior education for children with disabilities.

Factors Affecting Inclusive Practices

According to Erzincan journal of education faculty on sentiments, attitudes, and concerns about inclusion, early years in teacher education programs written by Mustafa Cansiz, Nurcan Cansiz (2018) There are number of factors which favour or inhibit successful inclusive practices, first is the students’ attitudes toward disabled peers, teachers’ beliefs and their self-efficacies, the degree of administrative support, prior training, teachers’ years of experience and lastly is teachers’ attitudes. Among them teachers’ attitudes is one of the most important contributing factors to successful inclusive practices.

Challenges of Inclusive Education

According to Furuta (2006) the challenges faced by the teachers include the management of children with various ‘disabling’ conditions, presence of students of different ages in the same classroom and the lack of support staff.

Kern (2006) stated that teachers who are ill-prepared or uncomfortable with the concept of inclusion may pass that discontent onto the students, which in turn can undermine the confidence and success of those students. These challenges include the lack of trained personnel and materials, appropriate training, adequate funding, additional time for preparation, development of new skills and classroom sizes Shah, (2006).

Maxwell, Lim, & Early, (2006) stated that inadequate teacher preparation has raised a concern about the availability and accessibility of high quality inclusive early childhood programs with well-trained staff. There are many research study concluded that general education teachers benefit from training to support children with disabilities in mainstream classrooms Philpott et al., (2010). The more specialized training about inclusion teachers received, the more likely they were to show positive attitudes toward inclusion. Having sufficient knowledge of inclusive education enables teachers and school administrators to become more flexible and productive according to Naicker, (2006). From the example of, deBettencourt, (1999); Jeon & Peterson, (2003) early childhood pre-service teachers who have taken coursework and had field experiences related to disabilities and inclusion showed a gain in their perceived attitudes, knowledge, and skills in working with children with disabilities.

Hastings and Oakford (2003) also found that in order for teachers to provide a variety of accommodations they needed ongoing professional development opportunities to continue to develop their skills. Such opportunities could include attending workshops, observing in other classrooms, reviewing research on inclusion, and collaboration with colleagues to develop a successful inclusion program.

A study by Leyser and Tappendorf (2001) also supported Hastings and Oakford's findings that teachers needed to attend various workshops and in-services to learn more about students with disabilities and inclusion. If teachers are provided with adequate training they will begin to feel more comfortable working with students with disabilities and implementing various accommodations within their classrooms. The lack of adequate training and the need for on-going Continued Professional Development (CPD) training was needed to enable better awareness and competence on how to best support children with special needs.

Successful implementation of inclusive education involves teachers to have the necessary knowledge, skills, competencies and support to accommodate a wide range of diversity among learners in an inclusive classroom Mthembu, (2009). Successful inclusion depends on the attitudes and actions of school principals according to Zollers, Ramanathan & Yu, (1999). The investment of other school personnel as they create the school culture and have the ability to challenge or support inclusion Ainscow, (2002). The school climate needed for inclusive education comprises four elements: successful classroom management, effective instructional techniques, appropriate accommodative practices, and instructional flexibility (Fazal, 2012). And it also important that the school leaders should encourage positive attitudes toward inclusion by encouraging the development of support groups within the school for other students or parents (Pivik, Mccomas, & Laflamme, 2002) .

In a study of Vignes, et. al (2009) Teachers who have positive attitudes may set the tone for the effective implementation of inclusion and create a positive social emotional climate in the classroom, in general, which may be directly or indirectly related to children's positive attitudes toward disabilities and how to best support children with special needs. Sixty-four percent of support professionals within the inclusion classrooms indicated the need for continued professional development (Liston, Nevin, & Malian, 2009). However, having the right amount of relevant knowledge and skills to get children with special needs where they ought to be is a necessary condition for the practitioners of inclusive education to succeed in the tricky terrain of inclusion according to Adjodhia-Andrews, (2007).

Another challenges is that the teachers in inclusive education facing in are the lack of trainings, regular students 'attitudes towards disabled peers, lack of support from the administrations and lack of appropriate materials used in their teaching learning process.

Mastropieri & Scruggs, (2001) stated that the most successful general education classrooms include teachers, co-teachers, paraprofessionals, and educational support to facilitate inclusion and adapt instruction for those students who need more educational assistance. From Bornman and Rose (2010:7), a general lack of support and resources, as well as the prevailing negative attitudes toward disability, all contribute to the general bewilderment in South African schools towards inclusion. Support is a necessary component of successful inclusive education practices as the needs of many learners with disabilities are beyond the basic services available in typical general education classes Lomofsky & Lazarus, (2001).

Polat (2011:57) suggested that resources and improved infrastructure are necessary but not sufficient for inclusion and that hanging attitudinal barriers among school professionals and in the wider community is one of the essential aspects of making inclusive education happen in low-income countries. Initial funding will be necessary while schools locate out-of-school learners, buy devices for learners who need them, make the needed infrastructure changes to accommodate a diverse body of learners, and hire specialists who will provide specialized systemic support to teachers and schools that need assistance Wildeman&Nomdo, (2007).

To face the challenges of preparing teachers for the increased accountability and more diverse learning needs, Philpott et al. (2010) identified the following six areas that school leaders should focus professional development on inclusive policy, diversity, nurturing positive attitudes, evidence-based teaching strategies, collaborative teaching, and meaningful teaching. Teachers rely on professional learning to increase their skills and knowledge. Based on a review literature of

Archibald, Coggshall, Croft, and Goe (2011) they identified the following characteristics of high-quality professional learning

1. Alignment with school goals, state and district standards and assessments, and other professional learning activities including formative teacher evaluation
2. Focus on core content and modelling of teaching strategies for the content
3. Inclusion of opportunities for active learning of new teaching strategies
4. Provision of opportunities for collaboration among teachers
5. Inclusion of embedded follow-up and continuous feedback. (p. 3)

Simon and Black (2011) suggested that in order for professional learning to impact student achievement it must be ongoing, incorporate training in multiple contexts, provide teachers with the opportunities to implement new skills and strategies, and provide teachers with feedback. The Curriculum and instructional modifications and progress monitoring is highly advised. There must be specialized training, and experience related to inclusion are deemed to equip teachers with more appropriate and in-depth knowledge and skills with which they can create more enriched and positive learning environments for all children.

Those knowledge and skills also help teachers address different abilities and needs in the classroom (Division for Early Childhood [DEC], (2014); DEC/National Association for the Education of Young Children [NAEYC], (2009); Gartin et al., 2001; Gemmell-Crosby &Hanzlik, (1994); Hsien, Brown, &Bortoli, (2009); Mulvihill, Shearer, & Van Horn, (2002). Hsien et al., (2009) also claimed that training opportunities provide basic knowledge of inclusion and help teachers learn effective pedagogical approaches and instructional adaptations necessary to work in an inclusive classroom the more skilful and knowledgeable they were in modifying their curriculum and adapting the environment for children with disabilities.

The more specialized training about inclusion teachers received, the more likely they were to show positive attitudes toward inclusion Buell et al., 1999; Gartin et al., 2001; Gemmell-Crosby &Hanzlik, 1994; Hsien et al., (2009); Mulvihill et al., (2002) .

While inclusion policy has been already adopted in the Philippines, many school teachers have yet to fully appreciate the value of inclusive education Muega&Echavia, (2011).With regard to the Sri Lankan context, the National Policy on Disability in Sri Lanka Ministry of Social Welfare, (2003) outlines barriers of environmental and transportation accessibility, communication, culture, the scarcity of assistive technology devices and societal and family expectations as impeding the implementation of inclusion.

Overcoming Barriers to Inclusive Education

In a journal article entitled Inclusive Education and Effective Classroom Practices by Editor: C.J.W. Meijer, In framing policies in this area, countries must take into account the fact that ensuring access for persons with disabilities to education and information requires various accommodations and modifications. Variables such as language, literacy, urban versus rural, cultural traditions and gender all must be taken into consideration in planning for effective inclusive Education. In addition, policy measures should seek to dismantle the heightened levels of exclusion from education faced by persons with impairments, such as intellectual or sensory impairments. To be successful, legislative and policy measures should specifically seek to dismantle each of the many barriers to inclusive education faced by persons with disabilities.

The Role Of Teachers And Educators In Inclusive Education

Teachers are critical actors in inclusive education and have a tremendous influence on the quality of education that a child receives. In many cases teachers are under-resourced, working in over-crowded classrooms and lacking the capacity to

adequately address the needs of all students. Inclusion requires sufficient numbers of teachers who are adequately prepared and trained.

Teachers should receive support to make possible inclusive approaches, with specialist teaching support where necessary. Teachers should also receive training, including on policies and strategies to promote the right of persons with disabilities to participate in the educational process at all levels, and finally to enable them to adapt the educational environment to meet a range of learning needs.

Such training may include, as relevant, a focus on utilization of accessible technology, where available, to enhance the educational experience of students with disabilities. Ensuring that persons with disabilities can become teachers can both bring in specialist skills and understanding, and can make a strong contribution to reducing discrimination, giving all children role models of inclusion.

Classroom Practice and Teacher Factors

In the journal article entitled *Inclusive Education and Effective Classroom Practices* by Editor: C.J.W. Meijer, states that the important prerequisites for special needs education within mainstream setting are the teachers' attitudes, available instruction time, the knowledge and skills of teachers, teaching methods and materials.

Stress

Selye, (1994) viewed stress as the common denominator of all adaptive reactions in the body and complete freedom from stress as death. In his first publication on stress in *Nature* in 1936, Selye defined stress as the nonspecific response of the body to any demand made on it accordingly he defined stress as a state manifested by a specific syndrome which consists of all the non-specifically induced changes within the biological system. He proposed that such changes were measurable and occurs at both the system and the local level. The entire stress process at the system level, including the threat and the individual's reaction to it, he called it as the general adaptation syndrome. To derive a conceptualization of stress, Selye chose to describe what it was not. He wrote that stress is not:

1. Simply nervous tension; it can occur in organisms without nervous systems or in anesthetized or unconscious patients.
2. An emergency discharge of hormones from the adrenal medulla; although catecholamines are a part of the stress reaction, they are not the only hormones activated, and they play no role in generalized inflammatory diseases or local stress reactions.
3. Everything that causes a secretion of the adrenal cortex (i.e., corticoids); adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH) can stimulate the release of corticoids without producing a stress response.
4. Always the nonspecific result of damage; normal activities, such as tennis or a passionate kiss, can produce a stress response without conspicuous damage.
5. The same as a deviation from homeostasis (Cannon, 1932), the body's steady state: Reactions to loud noises, blinking of the eye, or contracting a muscle may cause deviations from the resting state without evidence of a generalized stress reaction.
6. Anything that causes an alarm reaction: It is the stressor that is the stimulus and not the stress itself.
7. identical with the alarm reaction: These reactions are characterized by certain end-organ changes caused by stress and, hence, cannot be stress.
8. A nonspecific reaction: The pattern of the stress response is specific, although its cause and effects may vary.
9. Necessarily bad: The stress of success, challenge, and creativity is positive, whereas that of failure, anxiety, and infection can be negative.
10. To be avoided: Stress cannot be avoided. It is ubiquitous; it is an essential ingredient of life.

Stress

According to Lazarus (1984) stress is not defined as a specific kind of external stimulation nor a specific pattern of physiological, behavioral, or subjective reactions. Instead, stress is viewed as a relationship between individuals and their environment.

Factors Related to Stress

Gordon (1991) observed that stress refers to a psychological and physiological state that results when certain features of an individual's environment, including noise, pressure, job promotions, monotony, or the general climate attack or interrupts on that person. The discourse on stress has also been undertaken from a number of angles ranging from the conceptual understanding of stress, to its causes, effects and its management once it has reached uncomfortable levels (Selye 1974, 1980).

According to Kyriacou, (2001) Teacher stress has been defined within the literature as a negative affective experience that is related to one's ability to cope with job-related stressors. Similar to social-cognitive theories of stress Lazarus & Folkman, (1984), teachers experience stress when a situation is appraised as threatening this include job evaluation via student test performance relative to the ability to change or improve the said situation.

According to Berryhill, Linney, & Fromewick, (2009) Teacher stress may result from inadequate time and resources to prepare for the annual, high-stakes test, insufficient administrative support and unrealistic expectations of student test performance from parents von der Embse et al., (2015).

Fimian & Fastenau (1990) have emphasized that teacher stress are consists of emotional manifestations, physical manifestations, and work-related pressures.

Schwarzer & Hallum, (2008) also claimed that one of the causes of stress is uncomfortable subjective experiences in the workplace. Another cause of stress from McCarthy, & Abbott-Shim, (2001), is Appraisals of classroom resources and needs. Roeser et al., (2013) revealed that the physiological symptoms of stress are high cortisol levels and resting heart rate

Although many educators report a high level of job satisfaction, teachers also consistently report relatively high levels of job stress Chaplain, (2008); according to Schwarzer & Hallum, (2008). Job-related stressors are the strongest predictor of poor job satisfaction for teachers. Locke, (1969), defined Job satisfaction, as the enjoyment and fulfilment derived from work activities.

According to Billingsley & Cross, (1992), Low job satisfaction is associated with an increased likelihood of absenteeism and illness. From Collie, Shapka, & Perry, (2012) low morale stress among teachers and from Ingersoll, (2001) there is intent to leave the profession. Teachers are the greatest human capital resource in a school. In addition, (Perie & Baker, (1997) claimed that teacher recruitment and professional development in the early years can be costly, and when teachers leave the profession prematurely, schools are unable to obtain a return on those investments and that is because of the stress that teachers are experiencing in the academe.

Given the high cost of teacher burnout and attrition, it is essential to understand predictors of job satisfaction. A wealth of research has demonstrated that teachers are satisfied with the aspects of their jobs that involve instruction and direct interactions with students. In the study of Crossman & Harris, (2006); von der Embse et al., (2015). They claimed that teachers often appear to be dissatisfied with other conditions like the poor climate, annual evaluations based upon test performance and this seems to influence job performance.

In the study of Ballantine 1997 the sources of teacher stress are conceivably many. LeCompte and Dworkin (1991) remarks that sources of teacher stress can even include cultural and structural features of the school. Some wellorganised schools ironically stress teachers by lacking the appropriate flexibility which teachers need in their work. Dworkin (2001) appealed that some of the teachers stress is relative in decline in the status of the teacher pay packets of the teacher both at school level and in universities the specific work environment for teachers has also been found to be stressful. Another study from Jarvis (2002) has noted that long hours and heavy workloads were issues of special concern to teachers in England.

Moore (2000) also noted that there were stressful problems in scheduling, allocation of time for various classes and activities and the physical layout of the school. In his inspiring work in Zimbabwe, Nhundu (1999) he found that the major sources of stress for teaching professionals included high workload, lack of resources, overcrowded classrooms and perceived lack of government support. Teacher personality factors and leadership styles have also been implicated in causing stress for teachers.

Revell 2002 also cited that the negative aspects of stress are staggering. He states that in Britain 13 million working days were lost to stress. He also adds that 667 million British pounds were lost to such palliative measures as massage, yoga and certain other therapies that fell short of addressing the root causes of stress.

Chaplain (2008) and Kyriacou and Kunc (2007) argue that because of stress in the teaching Profession the attrition rate of teachers has reached alarming proportions in some parts of the world. Specific effects of stress in Australia have been reported in the form of large numbers of teachers who are discharged on grounds of ill health through a combination of psychological and physical effects of work-related stress. There have also been different responses by teachers to stress. Some of these include the Seeking of social support and involvement in entertainment that takes away the focus from the stressful atmosphere in the teaching profession Chireshe and Mapfumo (2003) Mapfumo et al (2012).

In the study of Billingsley (2004) in a comprehensive thematic analysis of studies investigating possible contributory factors to teachers' attrition and retention, suggested that work environment factors, such as low salaries, poor climate, lack of administrative support, and role problems, can lead to negative affective reactions such as high levels of stress, low levels of job satisfaction, and reduced organisational and professional commitment, which in turn could lead to withdrawal and eventually attrition.

In the study of Fimian&Fastenau,(1990), they stated that teacher stress consists of emotional manifestations, physical manifestations, and work-related pressures. Another source of stress for the teachers according to Schaubman, Stetson &Plog, (2011) is the increased in workload and dealing with parents of students with special needs and attempting to meet the parents' expectations. From Younghusband, Gurlie &Chruch (2003) stated that source of stress among teachers are not have training necessary to meet the needs of special needs students include in their classroom.

Stress on the Rise for Women

Form the report similar average stress levels; women are more likely than men to report that their stress levels are on the rise. They are also much more likely than men to report physical and emotional symptoms of stress. When comparing women with each other, there also appears to be differences in the ways that married and single women experience stress.

Women are more likely than men (28 percent vs. 20 percent) to report having a great deal of stress (8, 9 or 10 on a 10-point scale). Almost half of all women (49 percent) surveyed said their stress has increased over the past five years, compared to four in 10 (39 percent) men.

Women are more likely to report that money (79 percent compared with 73 percent of men) and the economy (68 percent compared with 61 percent of men) are sources of stress while men are far more likely to cite that work is a source of stress (76 percent compared with 65 percent of women).

Women are more likely to report physical and emotional symptoms of stress than men, such as having had a headache (41 percent vs. 30 percent), having felt as though they could cry (44 percent vs. 15 percent), or having had an upset stomach or indigestion (32 percent vs. 21 percent) in the past month.

Married women report higher levels of stress than single women, with one-third (33 percent) reporting that they have experienced a great deal of stress in the past month (8, 9 or 10 on a 10-point scale) compared with one in five (22 percent) of single women. Similarly, significantly more married women report that their stress has increased over the past five years (56 percent vs. 41 percent of single women). Single women are also more likely than married women to say they feel they are doing enough to manage their stress (63 percent vs. 51 percent).

In the of study conducted by Lunau et al (2015) in their research article entitled The Association between Education and Work Stress: Does the Policy Context Matter. They analyse associations between education and work stress in a large sample of workers from 16 European countries. They confirmed that a rather robust social gradient of stressful work in terms of low control and effort-reward imbalance, where those with lower educational qualification had higher levels of stressful work.

Another study conducted by the American Psychological Association (2008) accordingly, though they report similar average stress levels, female are more likely than male to report that their stress levels are on the rise. Female are also much more likely than male to report physical and emotional symptoms of stress. Accordingly, the most important for female is Having a good relationship with their family, having good relationships with their friends, doing well in their career or studies, able to manage stress, eating healthy foods, getting enough sleep and being physically active or fit. If those things are not on their system they have the tendency to get stress.

On the other hand, as cited by Robert M. Klassen University of Alberta Ming Ming Chiu State University of New York at Buffalo (2010) Female teachers had greater stress from both workload and student behaviors during class and lower self-efficacy for classroom management.

Other variables that May Lead to Increased Teacher Stress

In a study by Beck &Garguillo, (2001), Billingsley (2004), Eloff, Engelbrecht Oswald &Swart (2003) International research has advised that teaching has become one of the most stressful professions in recent years. However the reasons behind this proclaimed increase stress have been attributed to a number of different variables. The variables to be

considered in this study are teachers' life orientation, perceived self-efficacy, and the educational level being taught that being primary or secondary level of education and the last is the number of students in the class with special needs.

The first variable according to Li (2012) stated that the life orientation is simply a measure of a persons' dispositional optimism. Optimism has been defined by Scheier & Carver, (1985) as the favourability of a persons' generalized outcome expectancy. This would suggest that educators with a more positive outlook in general were better equipped to cope with change and challenges such as inclusive education. According to Younghusband et al (2003) Teachers appeared at time to work in a negative culture or if they exposed daily to negativity then perhaps this will impact their overall outlook on the job and facilitate low morale and the growth of a negative attitude towards their work.

The second variable in a study by Gibson & Dembo, (1984) teachers with a higher self-efficacy have been to be more positive and responsive to students. Greenwood, Olejnik, & Parkay, (1990) stated that they are experiencing a lower level of stress. According to Glenn (1994) teacher with self-efficacy shows less anger about negative or disruptive student behaviour. So therefore in order to reduce the level of stress in the teaching profession a teacher must have a high collective efficacy.

The third variable is the number of special Needs Students in the Classroom. The study suggested although overall there was a higher stress rating in educators teaching a class with a high number of special needs students.

Lastly is the educational level taught, according to William & Gersch (2004) they found that the younger the age group taught the lower the stress level? Meaning it is possible that younger children may be easier to control than older children and are more willing to view the teacher as a complete authoritative figure in comparison to older children who may not have the same level of respect or admiration for the adult teacher. Or perhaps the curriculum being taught to younger children is easier to roll out for an adult teacher to a young child in comparison to the older age group curriculum.

Causes of Stress

Stress affects people in various ways. The experience of work stress can cause unusual and dysfunctional behaviour at work and contribute to poor physical and mental health. In extreme cases, long term stress or traumatic events at work may lead to psychological problems and psychiatric disorders resulting in absence from work and preventing the worker from being able to Work again.

In a study by Hon. Soodesh S. Callichur Minister of Labour, Industrial Relations, Employment and Training Different stress-related factors have the potential of causing harm to the individual worker and ultimately to the organisation. Accordingly, some common job stressors encountered at the workplace include: Job Content, e.g. monotonous tasks, Unpleasant tasks. Workload and work pace. Having too much or too little to do, Working under time pressures, time constraints, inability to meet deadlines at work, Working Hours, e.g., Strict and inflexible working schedules, Long and unsocial hours, Unplanned working hours, Badly-designed shift systems, Lack of participation in decision making, Lack of decision over work methods, work pace, working hours and the work environment (including safety and health aspects), Career developments, status and pay, Job insecurity promotional issues, Piece rate payments schemes, Unclear and unfair performance evaluation systems, Being over-skilled or under-skilled for the job.

In terms of the Role in the organization causes are unclear roles, Conflicting roles within the same job, dealing with people and their problems. Interpersonal relationships, Inadequate, inconsiderate or unsupportive supervision, Poor relationship with co-workers, Bullying, harassment and violence, Isolated or solitary work, No agreed/unclear procedures for dealing with problems or complaints. Organizational culture, poor leadership, poor communication, lack of clarity about organizational objectives and structure. When it comes to Home-Work interface, Conflicting demands of work and home, Lack of support for domestic problems at work, Lack of support for work problems at work and lastly is stress at home.

Effects of Stress

The effects of stress have also been identified as wide ranging according to Eskridge and Coker (1985) he said that there were personal level symptoms of stress, it may be in the form of headaches, backaches, indigestion, sleep problems, chest pains, obsessive behaviour, inability to concentrate, heart disease, stroke, severe depression, and hallucinations. Another effects of stress according to Leka et al.(2003) in organizational level include: increasing absenteeism, decreasing commitment to work, increasing staff turnover, impairing performance and productivity, increasing complaints from clients and customers and damaging the organisation's image both among its workers and externally.

Chaplain (2008) and Kyriacou and Kunc (2007) argued that because of stress in the teaching profession, the abrasion rate of teachers has reached alarming proportions in some parts of the world. Specific effects of stress in Australia have been

reported in the form of large numbers of teachers who are out-dated on grounds of ill health through a combination of psychological and physical effects of work-related stress.

According to Soodesh S. Callichurn Minister of Labour, Industrial Relations, Employment and Training, when a person is affected by work-related stress people may become increasingly distressed and irritable, give low performance, have difficulty to concentrate, to think logically and to make decisions, become unable to relax or concentrate, enjoy their work less and feel less committed to it feel tired, depressed and anxious, experience sleep disturbances, experience serious health problems, such as: Heart disease, Disorders of the digestive system, Increase in blood pressure, Headache, Musculoskeletal disorders, Workers under stress are more prone to accidents at work. They find it difficult to maintain a healthy work-life balance. Consequently, they may engage in unhealthy activities, such as smoking, alcohol drinking, drug abuse and risky behaviours which may expose them to risk of contracting HIV/AIDS. Stress may also affect the immune system, impairing people's ability to fight infections. Stress can also lead to violent behaviour.

Managing Work-related Stress

In a study by Carter (1994) the stress management strategies used by mainstream and special needs education teachers were in line with the findings. He found that teachers employed relaxation exercises, organizing and setting priorities, maintaining diet and exercise, discussing problems with professional colleagues and taking days off. Sharing problems with relatives and friends is a typical human response and it has been found that social support at work was associated with lower blood pressure and that blood pressure rose in time when the social support was not there.

According to Hon. Soodesh S. Callichurn Minister of Labour, Industrial Relations, Employment and Training, Stress can be managed at two levels: first is the Individual level and

Second is the Organisational level. An individual can manage work-related stress by considering the following factors. Recognition of warning signs of excessive stress at work In order to be able to manage stress one has to be able to recognize warning signs and symptoms of stress which might include:

- a) Feeling anxious, irritable, or depressed;
- b) Inability to concentrate;
- c) Muscle tensions/headache;
- d) Social withdrawal;
- e) Using alcohol or drugs to cope with the situation.

From all these symptoms an individual who is under stress may adopt a healthy lifestyle. A healthy lifestyle might include:

- (a) Regular exercise/Relaxation exercise;
- (b) A balanced diet;
- (c) Getting enough sleep - It is important to improve the quality of sleep;
- (d) Getting support - close relationships such as family and friends are vital in helping one through times of stress. Moreover a person who is under stress should know prioritizing and organizing this can be achieved through:
 - (a) Time management - create a balanced schedule; do not over-commit; try to leave earlier in the morning.
 - (b) Task management - prioritize tasks, tackle tasks in order of importance; break projects into small steps; delegate responsibility when needed; be willing to compromise where possible.

Accordingly, another ways to decreased level of stress is improving emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence is the ability to manage and use the emotions in positive and constructive ways. It is about communicating with others in ways that draw people to us, overcome differences, repair wounded feelings, and defuse tension and stress. When it comes to satisfaction and success at work, emotional intelligence matters just as much as intellectual ability.

Emotional intelligence in the workplace has four major components namely: Self-awareness, Selfmanagement, Social awareness and Relationship management. Some key skills needed to raise one's emotional intelligence and manage stress at work include Realizing when one is stressed and recognize the particular stress response, Recognizing and effectively using non-verbal cues and body language and Developing the capacity to meet challenges with humour. Resolving conflicts positively and in a healthy and constructive way can strengthen trust between people and relieve workplace stress and tension.

Breaking bad habits

In a study of Soodesh S. Callichurn Minister of Labour, Industrial Relations, Employment and Training, Negative thoughts and behaviour make job stress worse. He suggested the ways of breaking the bad habits Namely: Flip negative thinking,

Don't try to control the uncontrollable, Clean up the workstation, Take time away - take a quick break and move away from the stressful situation, Talk it over with someone - sharing thoughts and feelings with a trustworthy person can help reduce stress, Connect with others at work – encourage colleagues to support each other, Look for humour in the situation when used appropriately, because they say that humour is a great way to relieve stress in the workplace. Employees should accept opportunities for medical treatment and counselling whenever recommended.

Specific patterns of primary and secondary appraisal lead to different kinds of stress.

In a study of Lazarus and Folkman (1984) he distinguished Three types of stress includes harm, threat, and challenge. Harm refers to the (psychological) damage or loss that has already happened. Threat is the anticipation of harm that may be imminent. Challenge results from demands that a person feels confident about mastering. These different kinds of psychological stress are embedded in specific types of emotional reactions, thus illustrating the close conjunction of the fields of stress and emotions.

Lazarus (1991) distinguished 15 basic emotions. Nine of these are negative such as anger, fright, anxiety, guilt, shame, sadness, envy, jealousy, and disgust. While the four positive emotions are happiness, pride, relief and love. The last two emotions are hope and compassion.

Eight groups of coping strategies according to Lazarus and his Co-workers

1. confrontative coping,
2. distancing,
3. self-controlling,
4. seeking social support,
5. accepting responsibility,
6. escape-avoidance, 7.painful problem- solving,
8. Positive reappraisal.

Coping With Stress

Selye, the founder of Stress theory, defined coping as adapting to stress situations. He wrote that by removing stressors from our lives, by not allowing certain neutral events to become stressors, by developing a proficiency in dealing with conditions we do not want to avoid, and by seeking relaxation or diversion from the demand.

Essential Points Of Selve's Model Of Stress

1. All life events cause some stress.
2. Stress is not bad per se, but excessive or unnecessary stress should be avoided whenever possible.
3. The stressor is the stimulus eliciting a need for adaptation; stress is the response.
4. The nonspecific aspects of the body's reaction to an agent may not be as obvious as the specific effects. Sometimes, only disease ordysfunction will make an individual realize that he or she is under stress.
5. Stress should be monitored through a battery of parameters.
6. Stress should not be equated with only ACTH, corticoid, or catecholamine secretions. These seem to manifest the main pathways of nonspecific adaptation; they are but a few of the elements of a very complex scheme, however.
7. Removal of the stressor eliminates stress.

Stress, Disease, and Illness

According to Selye (Tache& Selye, 1985), the nervous and hormonal responses to stressors, as discussed previously, aid survival. He believed the demand-induced neuron-hormonal changes are carefully balanced to enhance the organism's capacity to meet challenges and, thus, are adaptive. If, however, there is an excess of defensive or submissive bodily reactions, then diseases of adaptation can occur.

Conditions in which such maladaptation is a factor include high blood pressure, diseases of the heart and blood vessels, diseases of the kidney, eclampsia, rheumatic and rheumatoid arthritis, inflammatory diseases of the skin and eyes, infections, allergies and hypersensitivity diseases, nervous and mental diseases, sexual dysfunctions, digestive diseases, metabolic diseases, cancer, and diseases of a compromised immune system. Simonton and Creighton (1978) and Goodkin, Antoni, and Blaney (1986) proposed that there is a strong relationship between stress and cancer. And from Matthews and Glass (1981) suggested a similar relationship between stress and heart disease.

Preventive Coping Skills

Teachers cope with school stress in many different ways. Sorenson (1999) suggested Simple tactics that can help a teacher control stress such as a balanced diet, exercise, adequate Sleep, as well as being able to recognize work overload and stress-resistant workplaces. Certain Coping mechanisms can also have a negative effect on a person's mental health. In a study of Suldo, Shaunessy, & Hardesty (2008) Relieving stress using anger-induced methods such as placing blame on others and yelling can increase mental health problems such as insomnia, anxiety, and depression.

Self-Efficacy

In a study of Caprara, Barbaranelli, Steca, & Malone, (2006) Klassen & Chiu, (2010) In order to overcome those concerns high teacher efficacy has been found to be an important link between job-related stressors and job satisfaction.

Bandura (1997) defined Self-efficacy as the belief of one's capacity to complete a task successfully. He also defined Self-efficacy as a person's belief in his or her own competence to execute required behavior successfully to get expected results. If people do not believe in their own abilities in generating a desired effect through their acts, they will not have enough motivation to conduct the act. Accordingly, High self-efficacy is a predictor of increased motivation to achieve goals and feeling more comfortable in coping with unfavourable environments.,

Bandura (1986, p.391) described self-efficacy as peoples' judgement of their capabilities to organize and execute courses of action required attaining designated types of performances'.

In addition, Self-efficacy refers to a person's perceived capability, as distinct from functional ability, to perform a particular action or course of action. He mentioned that self-efficacy beliefs have a major role in changing behaviors, as these beliefs determine the decision making in performing a behavior, the effort spent, and the problems that arise throughout the process. Bandura (1993) pointed out that people with high self-efficacy tend to have greater cognitive resourcefulness, strategic flexibility, and effectiveness in managing their environment, and set motivating goals for themselves.

Bandura (2002), states that anticipation and outcome expectations can help to master a situation and achieved the desired targets. It has been noticed that teachers with a high level of self-efficacy have a positive attitude towards everything. They always have control on their emotions, as a result they seldom display their anger in front of their students and this attitude assures high achievement. Teachers with high level of self-efficacy are open to new methods and have the ability to adopt new techniques.

Bandura (1997) claimed that people with high self-efficacy are resilient and more motivational in challenging situations, the one with low self-efficacy can give up more easily and can lead to negative feelings such as stress, anxiety and these feelings may decrease the efficiency of individuals negatively or positively. Teachers with low self-efficacy levels experienced burnout.

In a study of Schwarzer & Jerusalem, (1995) self-efficacy is typically understood to be domain specific, yet is often measured as a general ability applicable across a wide range of situations.

According to Tschannen-Moran & Woolfolk Hoy, (2001) teacher efficacy is a job-specific extension of self-efficacy, and is defined by the judgment of an ability to bring about desired outcomes of student engagement and learning, even among those students who may be difficult or unmotivated. The quality of education will be achieved through the self-efficacy of teachers according to Tschannen Moral et al 1998:233. He defined teacher's self-efficacy as the teacher's belief in his or her capability to organize and execute courses of action.

He added that self-efficacy was a context specific and this should be considered while judging. Teachers with a high level of self-efficacy believe that they can teach difficult students effectively. The three factors of teaching efficacy, as identified by Tschannen-Moran and Woolfolk Hoy, have been linked to a variety of positive outcomes including higher job satisfaction Klassen & Chiu, (2010), use of effective teaching strategies Woolfolk Hoy &BurkeSpero, (2005), and greater well-being, Egyed& Short, (2006).

In a study by Schmitz & Schwarzer, 2000; Schwarzer &Hallum, (2008) teachers with high general self-efficacy choose to perform more challenging tasks. Zullig et al., (2011) pointed out that one aspect of self-efficacy little explored is social

self-efficacy he states that Social self-efficacy includes such skills as social boldness, participation in a social group or activity and friendly behaviors.

Social self-efficacy relates to individuals' ability to overcome social-oriented challenges and barriers according to Muris, (2001). Teacher self-efficacy is defined as 'the teacher's belief in his or her capability to organise and execute courses of action required to successfully accomplish a specific teaching task in a particular context therefore this should be considered while mediating teachers.

Teacher efficacy represents a promising area for new research to guide future intervention selection and support teachers in coping with the demands of high-stakes testing Curby et al., (2013). The teacher's perception of self-efficacy is also important in implementing inclusive education. And it has the effect on teaching activities. Pajares (1992) specifies that the strongest of teacher attitudes is teaching teacher efficacy.

In the study of Romi and Leyser (2006) they found that the group who completed special education major during its teacher education program showed a significantly higher level of perceived teaching-efficacy than the groups that lacked such experience.

In a study by Erdem&Demirel, (2007) Rom i&Leyser, (2006) Woodcock, (2008) Gender is also associated with perceived teaching-efficacy of pre-service teachers. Several studies have found that female teachers express a higher degree of perceived teaching-efficacy than their male counterparts. In a study of Mexican pre-service teachers, Forlin et al. (2010) also found that female pre-service teachers showed higher teaching -efficacy beliefs than their male counterparts.

Effect of the Self-Efficacy of Teachers

According to Moos and Acevedo (2009) there is a positive relationship among behavioural and psychological and computer self- efficacy. This point out that a high self- perceived efficacy equates to a better performance among teachers and students who have with high self-efficacy beliefs are more enthusiastic to teach and they put more effort into their teaching and they are willing to experiment new teaching methods. On the other hand, teachers with low self- efficacy beliefs tend to be more anxious about their instruction and they do not put much effort and easily give up when they encounter with obstacles (Schunck, 1981; Schunck, Hanson & Cox, 1987). Therefore it is needed to know that self-efficacy of teachers in order to evaluate the capacity of their knowledge in handling inclusive education.

Impact of Self-Efficacy

Self-efficacy is self-belief of teachers on their capabilities and trust they have on their methodologies to accomplish the tasks. In particular cases, self-efficacy gives a guarantee to teachers that they are able to transfer their knowledge to the students successfully. Teachers with a greater sense of self-efficacy beliefs are more willing to experiment new methods of teaching to meet the requirements of their students. Thus, sense of efficacy in a teacher has a strong positive impact on student performance according to Gosky (1988) Tschanne& Woolfolk (2001) contrary to the real sense of having self-efficacy, if teachers have a low sense of self-efficacy, their students will show poor performance.

Woolfolk (1998) says that self-efficacy is also related to the result of activities used in the classrooms. If teachers accomplish the task successfully, self-efficacy will increase while low level of teachers' self-efficacy leads to failure. He explained that teacher with high self-efficacy can still accomplish the task successfully despite of large class at hand and on the other hand, failure displays a low level of self-efficacy. Accordingly the most influential source of self-efficacy information is said to be the mastery level experiences of an individual, which one experiences directly.He explained that teacher with high self-efficacy can still accomplish the task successfully despite of large class at hand and on the other hand, failure displays a low level of self-efficacy. If a person accomplishes a given task, it means that self-efficacy beliefs are being promoted positively. On the other hand, failure displays a low level of self-efficacy.

Physiological and Emotional States

The physiological and emotional behaviour of teachers also affects teacher self-efficacy. If they are confident and enthusiastic about their actions, they will get positive and outstanding results. On the other hand, if teachers are depressed or anxious about their actions, this will produce negative results. Teacher confidence is highly significant because it has the ability to change the results. Even well-educated and qualified teachers are not successful if they have depressing thoughts or lack of confidence. Self-confidence has a strong relationship with self-efficacy in a way both are directly proportional to each other.

Ashton and Webb (1986) further explain that teachers who have a higher level of self-efficacy are more organized, have a greater skill of instruction and questioning, have better abilities to explain and can solve academic problems easily. On the

other hand, teachers with low level of Self-efficacy seem more confused, feel threaten to be questioned, cannot maintain tasks and feel difficulty in countering student affairs.

In a study of Woolfolk, Rosoff& Hoy (1990) teachers who have a high level of perceived teaching-efficacy use a range of behavior management techniques. They do more practical activities and follow effective teaching learning methods Guskey (1988) they also take more initiatives in order to meet learning needs of all students and set higher level of goals to be achieved by themselves and their students Mergler&Tangen (2010).

Lastly from Paneque&Barbetta (2006) teachers with high teaching-efficacy tend to show behavioural characteristics such as effort taking, decision making, keeping patience in challenging situations and also improving students' motivation, which results in their students' high achievement.

Sources of Teacher Self-Efficacy

Student achievement is linked to teacher self-eficacy, and there are tools created that can measure the specific self-eficacy of teachers. These measures have been scrutinized and developed over time. As reliable instruments are available, attention must be turned to the sources of teacher efficacy and how it is both stimulated and suppressed. In his earliest work, Bandura (1977) proposed that there are four major sources of efficacy and they are performance accomplishments, vicarious experience, verbal persuasion, and emotional arousal. Performance accomplishments are the direct experiences of participants in given situations and they influence self-eficacy by giving participants the opportunity to be exposed and desensitized to the performance task. It is also an opportunity for participants to instruct their own performance and learn from their own modelling. The second source, according to Bandura, is vicarious experience, and this is live and symbolic modelling. Vicarious experience is the when participants observe the experience of others and make comparisons to their own perceptions of their performance abilities (1977). Verbal persuasion involves suggestion, encouragement, and self-instruction, and although verbal persuasion is a common attempt at promoting self-eficacy, like vicarious experience, it is not as strong of a source self-eficacy as performance accomplishments (1977). The final source is emotional arousal, and this is another strong influence of self-eficacy, involving the agitation and stress that can overtake a participant before a given task (1977).

Bandura explained these four sources of self-eficacy within a broad context, but can also be explained within an educational context, which the upcoming research will explain.

According to Bandura (1977) sources of self-eficacy can be compartmentalized into four groups, and of those groups, three of them can be elicited through experience. That is, three sources of self-eficacy can be influenced by the experiences of the participant. Teacher working conditions are just that, as they are the characteristics of the experiences of working within a school. Many working conditions, such as professional development, collegiality, and school leadership are sources of self-eficacy for teachers.

Lastly, physiological factors such as getting excessively stressed in the demanding situations may have detrimental effect on self-eficacy. Self-eficacy has some important consequences for individuals. While the thinking of being able to overcome a task may arouse the feeling of satisfaction from the task, low efficacy can lead to negative feelings such as stress, anxiety and these feelings may decrease the efficiency of individuals negatively or positively. Moreover, whereas people with high self-eficacy are resilient and more motivational in challenging situations, the one with low self-eficacy can give up more easily.

Early research by Ashton (1984) found that “the isolation, the difficulty in assessing one’s effectiveness as a teacher, the lack of collegial and administrative support, and the sense of powerlessness that comes from limited collegial decision-making – make it difficult for teachers to maintain a strong sense of efficacy. Professional development is one source of self-eficacy for teachers, and it would fall mostly comfortably under Bandura’s second realm, vicarious experience, but also under his third realm, verbal persuasion. Professional development in mathematics education has shown increases in both teacher self-eficacy and student achievement Bruce, Esmonde, Ross, Dookie, & Beatty (2010).

Tschannen-Moran and McMaster’s (2009) study included the professional development of primary teachers for the purposes of reading instruction where coaching was involved. This research was similar to the work of Ross (1992) in that the professional development involved coaching. Tschannen-Moran and McMaster (2009) argued that the involvement of coaching would be an example of Bandura’s (1977) performance accomplishments realm, but as the coach can only give feedback and model, this claim is difficult to make. Regardless of which realm coaching can be found in, the research did find that those groups who had coaching accompanying their professional development were found to make gains in their

self-efficacy. Also of interest is the group that received no coaching after the professional development, experienced a decrease in their self-efficacy (2009) this could possibly be attributed to the strength of Bandura's (1977) fourth source of efficacy, emotional arousal, in that learning and teaching with new procedures may have created doubt of teachers' current habits and anxiety of teaching new processes.

Klassen and Chiu (2010) found that teachers' sense of efficacy increased from early career to mid-career, but then decreased after that. The years of experience could be attributed to the performance accomplishments realm, but as this is the strongest realm, self-efficacy would be expected to continually increase. This could be attributed to the strength of emotional arousal that occurs with the psychological and biological changes related to chronological age (2010). Their research also found disparity among participants teaching at different grade levels. Self-efficacy was strongest for those teaching at the youngest grade levels and decreased as student grade levels increased (2010).

The exact opposite was found to be true in research done by Raudenbush, Rowan, and Cheong (1992). With disparity among teachers working in the same school environment, and disparity among research findings, it is necessary to do further research on the differences of working conditions for teachers working with students from different grade levels.

Not only does self-efficacy differ between teachers from the same school, it was also found that teachers, themselves, differ in sense of efficacy from subject to subject or class to class. Based on Bandura's (1986) theory that self-efficacy is contextual and not merely a characteristic of an individual, the researchers found that the same teachers would have different levels of efficacy depending on the subject they taught and the level of students they were teaching. Teacher self-efficacy was higher when teaching students on higher academic "tracks", but it was also higher for teachers who reported higher levels of staff collaboration and control over instructional conditions (Raudenbush, et al., 1992). This once again speaks to the relationship between teacher working conditions and teacher self-efficacy.

Theoretical framework

The study was associated with the theoretical foundation of Bandura (1977) and Hans Selye (1907–1982) founder of the stress theory.

The Bandura's Theory of Self-Efficacy,

According to this theory changes in defensive behavior produced by different methods of treatment derive from a common cognitive mechanism. It is postulated that psychological procedures, whatever their format, serve as ways of creating and strengthening expectations of personal effectiveness. Perceived self-efficacy affects people's choice of activities and behavioral settings, how much effort they expend, and how long they will persist in the face of obstacles and aversive experiences. The stronger the perceived self-efficacy the more active the coping efforts. Performance accomplishments provide the most influential efficacy information because it is based on personal mastery experiences. The other sources of efficacy information include the vicarious experiences of observing others succeed through their efforts, verbal persuasion that one possesses the capabilities to cope successfully, and states of physiological arousal from which people judge their level of anxiety and vulnerability to stress.

Selye's Theory

Selye's (1936) proposal was that stress was present in an individual throughout the entire period of exposure to a nonspecific demand. He distinguished acute stress from the total response to chronically applied stressors, terming the latter condition 'general adaptation syndrome', which is also known in the literature as Selye's Syndrome. The syndrome divides the total response from stress into three phases: the alarm reaction, the stage of resistance and the stage of exhaustion. When individuals are exposed to a stressor, they are at first taken off guard, then attempt to maintain homeostasis by resisting the change, and eventually fall victim to exhaustion in countering the stressor.

Research Questions

The research was a descriptive quantitative that aimed to determine the stress levels and perceived self-efficacy of teachers handling in inclusive education. The participants of this study were the teachers of Bagong Nasyon II National High School located at Barangay San Isidro Antipolo City

Specifically, it sought to answer to the following research questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents with respect to?
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Sex
 - 1.3 Civil Status

- 1.4 Educational Attainment
- 1.5 Rank
- 1.6 Shift
- 1.7 Number of Seminars-Trainings attended related to Special Education
- 1.8 Length of Service
- 1.9 Number of learners with special educational needs being handled
2. What is the level of stress of the respondents with respect to profile?
3. What is the respondent's level of perceived self- efficacy with respect to profile?
4. Is there a significant difference in the stress levels and perceived self-efficacy with regards to profile?
5. Is there a relationship between respondent's stress levels and perceived self-efficacy with respect to inclusive education?

Hypotheses

There is no significant relationship between the level of stress and perceived self-efficacy of teachers handling inclusive education.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study was conducted to determine the stress levels and perceived self-efficacy of teachers handling inclusive education. The participants of this study were the teachers of Bagong Nayon II National High School located at Barangay San Isidro Antipolo City particularly those handling learners with special educational needs. The researcher looked into the respondents' demographics, the educational background of teachers, length of teaching experience, and personal encounter in handling students with special educational needs in inclusive education.

To define the level of stress and perceived self-efficacy of teachers handling inclusive education, the researcher utilized a structured questionnaire checklist. The first questionnaire is Teacher Profile Stress Questionnaire made by International Stress Management Association (ISMA) UK 2013. This test is intended to give an overview on the stress level of a person. The second tool used is the Teachers' Self-Efficacy Scale (TSES; Tschannen-Moran & Woolfolk Hoy 2001); it instructs respondents to rate their own efficacy for each of three areas of teaching like the classroom management, instructional practices, and student engagement). The use of this instrument has three domains (student engagement, classroom management, and instructional strategies) though was intended to measure the over-all self-efficacy of the respondents and not to identify the strengths and weaknesses but the relationship. Results obtained were interpreted to establish the relationship of perceived self-efficacy pertaining to the respondents' stress level.

Definition of Terms

Inclusive Education – An educational approach wherein learners with special needs are supported not just by the school but also their community which grants them equal educational opportunities as experienced by regular students.

Inclusion – An educational system wherein children with special needs are engaged in a regular classroom setting and valued as regular students.

Job stressors – Stimulants present at work that eventually affect the individual.

Learner- Student with special educational needs.

Mainstreaming – Practice of enrolling learners with mild or moderate disabilities into regular classes provided that they will have access to necessary support services.

Perceived teaching-efficacy – Measure of one's confidence level to obtain desired results out of student engagement and learning.

Stress – is a condition of mental or emotional strain brought about by adverse and difficult circumstances.

Teacher Stress – is a negative state particular to teachers triggered by job-related stressors.

Self-efficacy – One's confidence level in his ability to execute courses of action considering the current situation.

Teacher self-efficacy - An assessment of one's ability to obtain desired results out of student engagement and learning, regardless of the students' capacity and interest.

METHODOLOGY

This chapter discusses how the study was taken. It explains the method of research, the locale of the study, the respondents or subjects of the study and sampling technique, the data collection method, the data analysis and procedure and treatment of data.

Research Design

The study aimed to identify the level of stress and perceived self-efficacy of teachers handling inclusive education in Bagong Nayon II National High School.

The study employed the descriptive comparative method which involves gathering data that describe events and then organizes.

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted at Bagong Nayon II National High School, a public non-sectarian schools that operates Junior high school education located at Lower San Isidro, Barangay San Isidro Antipolo City, Rizal of CALABARZON (Region IV-A) caters students from Grade seven to ten and it was established year 2004. The school has seventy-seven (77) instructional rooms and two (2) non-instructional rooms, which are all powered by a power grid.

At present, there are five (5) non-teaching personnel and two hundred twelve (212) nationally funded Teachers under the management of Mr. Ronaldo I Ata as Principal III. The school presently operates on a two shift scheme and it caters five thousand three hundred two (5302) enrollees with one thousand five hundred forty five (1,545) Grade Seven (7), one thousand four hundred forty four (1,444), Grade Eight (8). One thousand two hundred thirty three (1,233) Grade nine (9) and one thousand eighty (1080) Grade 10.

The school aims to provide every student the best possible education in order to prepare the students for life beyond school where the school serves as a learning community which encourages staff, students, parents, and other stake holders to involve themselves and work as a team in realizing the mission, vision and core values of the department of Education.

Participants

Purposive sampling was used to select teachers who will be given test questionnaire

The selection criteria will be based on each teacher's potential to add the understanding of the process and procedures used to collect related data. The selected participants in Bagong Nayon II National High School for this bounded case will not be complicated.

There are a total of 212 teachers in Bagong Nayon II National High School and those handling learners with special educational needs in all grade level served as the respondents. The respondents of the study included only 40 teachers, combining 15 male and 25 female because they are the one handling learners with special educational needs. They will be requested to accomplish the survey questionnaire. These will be answered base on the teacher's profile; the level of stress adapted from Stress Questionnaire by International Stress Management Association (ISMA) UK 2013; and perceived self-efficacy of teachers adapted from Teachers' Sense of Self Efficacy Scale by Tschannen-Moran, M., & Woolfolk Hoy, A. (2001) handling inclusive education.

Research Instrument

A standardized questionnaire and researcher-made questionnaires were utilized for measuring the level of stress and teachers' perceived self-efficacy. Three sets of survey questionnaire were given by the researcher to the respondents. The first questionnaire is on teacher's profile which includes age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, rank, shift, seminars/trainings related to Sped, and the number of learners with special educational needs. The respondent filled in the space provided by checking the appropriate box.

The second questionnaire is Stress Questionnaire by International Stress Management Association (ISMA) UK 2013; this test is intended to give an overview on the level of stress of an individual. It was answered by yes or no and the Scoring scale will be:

SCORE	INTERPRETATION
4 points or less	You are least likely to suffer from stress-related illness
5 to 13 points	You are more likely to experience stress-related ill health either mental, physical or both; You would benefit from stress management / counselling or advice to help in the identified areas.
14 points or more	You are the most prone to stress showing a great many traits or characteristics that are creating unhealthy behaviors. This means that you are also more likely to experience stress & stress-related illness e.g. diabetes, irritable bowel, migraine, back and neck pain, high blood pressure, heart disease/strokes, mental ill health (depression, anxiety & stress). It is important to seek professional help or medical assistance. You may also consult with stress management counsellors for assessment and evaluation

The third questionnaire is Teachers' Sense of Self Efficacy Scale by Tschannen-Moran, M., & Woolfolk Hoy, A. (2001). It was used to assess teaching efficacy. The TSES is comprised of 12 items and includes three subscales that inquire about teacher's feeling of efficacy about engaging students in learning, providing varied and high quality instructional practices and managing the classroom. The first part consisted of items about the teachers' sense of self-efficacy and personal experience in handling learners with special educational needs. The second part consisted about the teacher's profile and length of teaching experience.

As we have used factor analysis to test this instrument, we have consistently found three moderately correlated factors:

- Efficacy in Student Engagement,
- Efficacy in Instructional Practices,
- Efficacy in Classroom Management,

At times, however, the make-up of the scales may vary slightly. It was recommended that the full scale 12-item short form be used, because the factor structure often is less distinct for the respondents.

The Subscale Scores, to determine the Efficacy in Student Engagement, Efficacy in Instructional Practices, and Efficacy in Classroom Management subscale scores, we compute unweight means of the items that load on each factor. Generally, these groupings are:

- Efficacy in Student Engagement: Items 2, 4, 7, 11
- Efficacy in Instructional Strategies: Items 5, 9, 10, 12
- Efficacy in Classroom Management: Items 1, 3, 6, 8

The Reliabilities In the study reported in Tschannen-Moran & Woolfolk Hoy (2001) above the following reliabilities were found:

	Mean	SD	alpha
TSES	7.1	.98	.90
Engagement	7.2	1.2	.81
Instruction	7.3	1.2	.86
Management	6.7	1.2	.86

Data Gathering

In the achievement of necessary information, the researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent and principal of Bagong Nasyon II National High School which required allowing the researcher to conduct survey for public school respondents. The letter of request duly signed and approved by the Dean of FEU- Roosevelt College Graduate School of Education was furnished and personally given to them.

The researcher distributed the questionnaire to the teachers who are handling learners with educational needs.

Data Analysis Procedure

The following statistical tools were utilized to analyze the gathered data.

To determine the teacher profile, descriptive statistics was used through the computation of frequency and percentage.

To determine teachers' Self- efficacy level, weighted mean and standard deviation was used.

To determine teachers' stress level, weighted mean and standard deviation was used.

To determine if there is no significant difference between the stress levels and a teachers' perceived self- efficacy independent test was used.

RESULTS

This chapter contains information about the results of the study and the analysis and interpretation of data gathered with the use of the adapted statistical measures. The presentation includes a narrative discussion of the results and implications of the data gathered which are illustrated in tables.

Problem No. 1 Profile of the participants with respect to:

- 1.1 Age
- 1.2 Sex
- 1.3 Civil Status
- 1.4 Educational Attainment
- 1.5 Rank
- 1.6 Shift
- 1.7 Number of Seminars-Trainings attended related to Special Education
- 1.8 Length of Service
- 1.9 Number of learners with special educational needs being handled

Table 1.1 Profile of the Participants in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
20-25 years old	8	20%
26-30 years old	16	40%
31-35 years old	4	10%
36-40 years old	11	27%
41-45 years old	1	3%
TOTAL	40	100%

Table 1.2 Profile of the Participants in terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	15	37.5%
Female	25	62.5%
TOTAL	40	100%

Table 1.3 Profile of the Participants in terms of Civil Status

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	22	55%
Married	18	45%
TOTAL	40	100%

Table 1.4
Profile of the Participants in terms of Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
BA/BS	12	30%
With units earned in MA/MS	25	62.5%
MA	2	5%
With units earned in PhD/EdD	1	2.5%
TOTAL	40	100%

Table 1.5 Profile of the Participants in terms of Rank

Rank	Frequency	Percentage
Teacher 1	32	80%
Teacher 2	5	12.5%
Teacher 3	3	7.5%
TOTAL	40	100%

Table 1.6 Profile of the Participants in terms of Shift

Shift	Frequency	Percentage
AM	30	75%
PM	10	25%
TOTAL	40	100%

Table 1.7
Profile of the Participants in terms of Number Seminars-Trainings

No. of Seminars-Trainings	Frequency	Percentage
1 – 3	17	42.5%
None	23	57.5%
TOTAL	40	100%

Table 1.8 Profile of the Participants in terms of Length of Service

Length of Service	Frequency	Percentage
1 – 5	18	45%
6 – 10	14	35%
11 – 15	6	15%
16 – 20	2	5%
TOTAL	40	100%

Table 1.9
Profile of the Participants in terms of Number of Learners with Special Educational Needsbeing handled

Number of Learners with Special Needs	Frequency	Percentage
1 – 5	38	95%
6 – 10	2	5%
TOTAL	40	100%

Problem No. 2 Stress Levels of The Respondents with Respect To Profile.

Table 2.1 Stress Levels of the Respondents in terms of Age

Age	Mean	SD	Interpretation
20-25 years old	13.13	3.44	More likely to experience stress
26-30 years old	12.63	5.16	More likely to experience stress
31-35 years old	12.50	4.51	More likely to experience stress
36-40 years old	11.09	4.72	More likely to experience stress
41-45 years old	13.00	2.30	More likely to experience stress
Over-all Mean	12.30	4.50	More likely to experience stress

Table 2.2 Stress Levels of the Respondents in terms of Sex

Sex	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Male	14.47	4.24	Most prone to stress
Female	11.00	4.21	More likely to experience stress
Over-all Mean	12.30	4.50	More likely to experience stress

Table 2.3 Stress Levels of the Respondents in terms of Civil Status

Civil Status	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Single	12.36	3.62	More likely to experience stress
Married	12.22	5.50	More likely to experience stress
Over-all Mean	12.30	4.50	More likely to experience stress

Table 2.4 Stress Levels of the Respondents in terms of Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Mean	SD	Interpretation
BA/BS	14.50	2.88	Most prone to stress
With units earned in MA/MS	11.48	4.93	More likely to experience stress
MA	12.50	0.71	More likely to experience stress
With units earned in PhD/EdD	6.00	0.56	More likely to experience stress
Over-all Mean	12.30	4.50	More likely to experience stress

Table 2.5 Stress Levels of the Respondents in terms of Rank

Rank	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Teacher 1	12.38	4.58	More likely to experience stress
Teacher 2	10.80	5.36	More likely to experience stress
Teacher 3	14.00	1.73	Most prone to stress
Over-all Mean	12.30	4.50	More likely to experience stress

Table 2.6 Stress Levels of the Respondents in terms of Shift

Shift	Mean	SD	Interpretation
AM	12.23	4.91	More likely to experience stress
PM	12.50	3.17	More likely to experience stress
Over-all Mean	12.30	4.50	More likely to experience stress

Table 2.7
Stress Levels of the Respondents in terms of Number Seminars-Trainings

No. of Seminars-Trainings	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1 – 3	11.65	3.72	More likely to experience stress
None	12.78	5.03	More likely to experience stress
Over-all Mean	12.30	4.50	More likely to experience stress

Table 2.8 Stress Levels of the Respondents in terms of Length of Service

Length of Service	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1 – 5	12.50	3.84	More likely to experience stress
6 – 10	12.93	5.31	More likely to experience stress
11 – 15	11.67	5.05	More likely to experience stress
16 – 20	8.00	0.00	More likely to experience stress
Over-all Mean	12.30	4.50	More likely to experience stress

Table 2.9 Stress Levels of the Respondents in terms of Number of Learners with Special Educational Needs being handled

Number of Learners with Special Needs	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1 – 5	10.50	4.53	More likely to experience stress
6 – 10	12.39	4.95	More likely to experience stress
Over-all Mean	12.30	4.50	More likely to experience stress

Problem No. 3 Respondent’s Perceived Self- Efficacy with respect to Profile.

Table 3.1 Perceived Self-Efficacy of the Respondents in terms of Age

Age	Mean	SD
20-25 years old	74.63	12.30
26-30 years old	71.06	18.59
31-35 years old	75.75	21.14
36-40 years old	79.91	13.76
41-45 years old	60.00	9.35
Over-all Mean	74.40	16.18

Table 3.2 Perceived Self-Efficacy of the Respondents in terms of Sex

Sex	Mean	SD
Male	74.40	17.01
Female	74.40	16.01
Over-all Mean	74.40	16.18

Table 3.3 Perceived Self-Efficacy of the Respondents in terms of Civil Status

Civil Status	Mean	SD
Single	75.91	14.36
Married	72.56	18.41
Over-all Mean	74.40	16.18

Table 3.4
Perceived Self-Efficacy of the Respondents in terms of Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Mean	SD
BA/BS	72.75	18.46
With units earned in MA/MS	74.80	15.73
MA	82.00	18.38
With units earned in PhD/EdD	69.00	8.16
Over-all Mean	74.40	16.18

Table 3.5 Perceived Self-Efficacy of the Respondents in terms of Rank

Rank	Mean	SD
Teacher 1	73.44	16.33
Teacher 2	70.60	15.49
Teacher 3	91.00	5.29
Over-all Mean	74.40	16.18

Table 3.6 Perceived Self-Efficacy of the Respondents in terms of Shift

Shift	Mean	SD
AM	73.73	17.49
PM	76.40	11.92
Over-all Mean	74.40	16.18

Table 3.7 Perceived Self-Efficacy of the Respondents in terms of Number Seminars-Trainings

No. of Seminars-Trainings	Mean	SD
1 – 3	78.00	13.27
None	71.74	17.84
Over-all Mean	74.40	16.18

Table 3.8
Perceived Self-Efficacy of the Respondents in terms of Length of Service

Length of Service	Mean	SD
1 – 5	72.07	19.64
6 – 10	74.83	13.09
11 – 15	76.83	20.47
16 – 20	79.50	3.54
Over-all Mean	74.40	16.18

Table 3.9 Perceived Self-Efficacy of the Respondents in terms of Number of Learners with Special Educational Needs being handled

Number of Learners with Special Needs	Mean	SD
1 – 5	74.05	16.53
6 – 10	81.00	1.41
Over-all Mean	74.40	16.18

Problem No. 4 Difference in the stress levels and perceived self-efficacy as regards to profile.

Table 4.1 Difference in the Stress Levels of the Respondents When Grouped According to Profile

Profile	Computed Values	Sig. (p-value)	Interpretation	Decision
Age	ANOVA Value = 0.272	0.894	Not Significant	Do not Reject Ho
Sex	T-test Value = 2.51	0.016	Significant	Reject Ho
Civil Status	T-test Value = 0.091	0.923	Not Significant	Do not Reject Ho
Educational Attainment	ANOVA Value = 2.036	0.126	Not Significant	Do not Reject Ho
Rank	ANOVA Value = 0.483	0.621	Not Significant	Do not Reject Ho
Shift	T-test Value = 0.161	0.874	Not Significant	Do not Reject Ho
Number of Seminars	T-test Value = -0.785	0.437	Not Significant	Do not Reject Ho
Length of Service	ANOVA Value = 0.331	0.569	Not Significant	Do not Reject Ho
Number of Learners	T-test Value = 0.565	0.569	Not Significant	Do not Reject Ho

Note: p-value $\leq$ 0.05 – significant, p-value $>$ 0.05 – not significant

Table 4.2 Difference in the Perceived Self-efficacy of the Respondents When Grouped According to Profile

Profile	Computed Values	Sig. (p-value)	Interpretation	Decision
Age	ANOVA Value = 0.671	0.616	Not Significant	Do not Reject Ho
Sex	T-test Value = 0.000	1.00	Not Significant	Do not Reject Ho
Civil Status	T-test Value = 0.647	0.521	Not Significant	Do not Reject Ho
Educational Attainment	ANOVA Value = 0.217	0.884	Not Significant	Do not Reject Ho
Rank	ANOVA Value = 1.852	0.171	Not Significant	Do not Reject Ho
Shift	T-test Value = -0.447	0.658	Not Significant	Do not Reject Ho
Number of Seminars	T-test Value = 1.218	0.331	Not Significant	Do not Reject Ho
Length of Service	ANOVA Value = 0.199	0.816	Not Significant	Do not Reject Ho
Number of Learners	T-test Value = 0.587	0.561	Not Significant	Do not Reject Ho

Note: p-value $\leq$ 0.05 – significant, p-value $>$ 0.05 – not significant

Problem No. 5 Relationship between Respondent’s Stress Levels and Perceived Self-Efficacy with respect to Inclusive Education.

Table 5 Relationship between Respondent’s Stress Levels and Perceived Self-Efficacy with Respect to Inclusive Education

Variable	Computed Pearson r Values	Meaning	Sig. (pvalue)	Interpretation	Decision
Stress Level vs. Perceived Self-Efficacy	-0.493	Moderately Strong Negative Correlation	0.012	Significant	Reject Ho

Note: p-value ≤ 0.05 – significant, p-value > 0.05 – not significant

DISCUSSION

Table 4.1 showed that age profile is not significant in determining stress level among the respondents with a significant value of 0.894. Assuming a significant level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected because the significant value is greater than the significant level (0.05). This means that age is not a determinant of stress level.

On the other hand, the present study revealed that the sex profile is significant in determining stress level among the respondents with a significant value of 0.016. Assuming a significant level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected because the significant value is below the significant level. This means that sex is a determinant of stress level. The result are not supported by the findings of Liu and Ramsey (2008) they found that women experience less job satisfaction than men, especially satisfaction from work conditions, and a number of researchers have noted that female teachers report higher stress than male teachers this was possibly due to higher levels of overall Workload Another study conducted by Robert M. Klassen University of Alberta Ming Ming Chiu State University of New York at Buffalo 2010 Female teachers had greater stress (from both workload and student behaviors during class) and lower selfefficacy for classroom management.

The civil status profile is not significant not significant in determining stress level among the respondents with a significant value of 0.923. Assuming a significant level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected because the significant value is greater than the significant level (0.05). This means that civil status is not a determinant of stress level. However in the study conducted by Johnson D (2015) he supported that the role of self-efficacy in marital life in his dissertation, found that high relationship value of self-efficacy was the best predictor of person’s expectations in marriage. On the basis of these studies we can say that self-efficacy is very essential variable or factor in married life.

The educational attainment profile is not significant in determining stress level among the respondents with a significant value of 0.126. Assuming a significant level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected because the significant value is greater than the significant level (0.05). This means that educational attainment is not a determinant of stress level.

The result was supported by the findings of The Price of Health 2007 survey from the Czech Republic where the results concluded that stress levels rise in accordance with the level of education, ranging from 13% of respondents with basic or no education stating that they suffered frequently from enormous stress, to over 38% for those with a university education.

The rank profile is not significant in determining stress level among the respondents with a significant value of 0.621. Assuming a significant level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected because the significant value is greater than the significant level (0.05). This means that rank is not a determinant of stress level. This is similar to the study in Luxembourg, the survey reported that 21% of higher position employees said they felt a high level of stress.

The shift profile is not significant in determining stress level among the respondents with a significant value of 0.874. Assuming a significant level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected because the significant value is greater than the significant level (0.05). This means that shift is not a determinant of stress level. The present study was supported by a Greek study, as it confirmed that sleep disturbance that occurs in shift work is strongly associated with chronic fatigue. The symptoms of fatigue, including sleepiness and lack of energy, impaired concentration, and feelings of discomfort, it’s supported that respondents who wake up early in the morning may feel those symptoms especially if they are not use to rise up early. Night shift in particular, is one of the most frequent reasons for the disruption of circadian rhythms, causing

significant alterations of sleep and biological functions, which can affect the physical and psychological well-being and negatively condition work performance.5–7.

Many studies have analyzed the impact of shift work on the physical health of workers. In particular, some authors identified these such as a maladaptation syndrome related to shift work, characterized by impaired sleeping/waking, gastrointestinal disorders, and an increased risk of cardiovascular diseases. Recently, a syndrome called “shift work disorder” has been identified by the presence of the following symptoms: alteration of circadian rhythm of sleep/wake, insomnia, excessive day sleepiness, and fatigue. daily shift workers reported the highest mean score (26.4 ± 4.2 SD), with a statistically significant difference (unpaired t-test, $P < 0.001$)

The number of seminars is not significant in determining stress level among the respondents with a significant value of 0.437. Assuming a significant level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected because the significant value is greater than the significant level (0.05). This means that seminar-training is not a determinant of stress level.

This study was supported by the study of Hastings and Oakford’s (2001) they found out that teachers needed to attend various workshops and in-services to learn more about students with disabilities and inclusion. Accordingly, if teachers are provided with adequate training they will begin to feel more comfortable working with students with disabilities and implementing various accommodations within their classrooms.

The length of service is not significant in determining stress level among respondents with a significant value of 0.569. Assuming a significant level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected because the significant value is greater than the significant level (0.05). This means that length of service is not a determinant of stress level. A recent study by Kooij et al. (2008) examined research on work motivation and aging and found that many age-related factors (i.e., chronological age, physical health, self-perception, social perception, skill obsolescence, and life stage) had a negative impact on the motivation beliefs of older workers. In addition, accordingly found that work motivation was influenced by an interaction of age-related factors. For instance, declining health may be related to a deterioration of self-concept or changes in weighting of work- and leisure-related values, motivation and result in reduced skills, The lower levels of older teachers’ self-efficacy beliefs may be influenced not only by biological and psychological changes related to chronological age but also by student and peer perceptions of declining competence influenced by stereotyped beliefs about aging. In sum, age-related changes in motivation beliefs, like self-efficacy, are influenced not only by chronological age but by the psychosocial context of the work environment.

The number of learners is not significant in determining stress level among respondents with a significant value of 0.569. Assuming a significant level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected because the significant value is greater than the significant level (0.05). This means that the number of learners is not a determinant of stress level. The present study was not supported by Zimbabwe, Nhundu (1999) he found that the major sources of stress for teaching professionals included overcrowded classrooms. This was also similar to the study of Hans Selye (1994) founder of stress theory he agreed that stress was present in an individual throughout the entire period of exposure to a nonspecific demand. Thus, the more stressors in the environment, the more chances that the individual acquired stress

Table 4.2 showed that respondent profile has minimal impact on their perceived self-efficacy.

The age profile is not significant in perceived self-efficacy level among the respondents with a significant value of 0.616. Assuming a significant level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected because the significant value is greater than the significant level (0.05). This means that age is not a determinant of perceived self- level. The result of the present study were supported by the earlier study conducted by Klassen and Chiu (2010) found that teachers’ sense of efficacy increased from early career to mid-career, but then decreased after that. The years of experience could be attributed to the performance accomplishments realm, but as this is the strongest realm, self-efficacy would be expected to continually increase. This could be attributed to the strength of emotional arousal that occurs with the psychological and biological changes related to chronological age (2010).

The sex profile is not significant in perceived self-efficacy level among the respondents with a significant value of 1.00. Assuming a significant level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected because the significant value is greater than the significant level (0.05). This means that sex is not a determinant of perceived self- level. The present study is similar to the study of Erdem&Demirel, (2007) Rom i&Leyser, (2006) Woodcock, (2008) as they found that sex is also associated with perceived teaching-efficacy of pre-service teachers. Several studies have found that female teachers express a higher degree of perceived teaching-efficacy than their male counterparts.

The civil status profile is not significant in perceived self-efficacy level among the respondents with a significant value of 0.521. Assuming a significant level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected because the significant value is greater than the significant level (0.05). This means that civil status is not a determinant of perceived self-level. The results supported by Johnson D (2015) he found out that high relationship value of self-efficacy was the best predictor of person's expectations in marriage. On the basis of these studies we can say that self-efficacy is very essential variable or factor in married life.

The educational attainment profile is not significant in perceived self-efficacy level among the respondents with a significant value of 0.884. Assuming a significant level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected because the significant value is greater than the significant level (0.05). This means that educational attainment is not a determinant of perceived self-level.

The rank profile is not significant in perceived self-efficacy level among the respondents with a significant value of 0.171. Assuming a significant level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected because the significant value is greater than the significant level (0.05). This means that rank is not a determinant of perceived self-level. The present study was supported by the study of Eiken and Saksvik (2009) have found that, the lower the position in job the lower levels of control over their jobs, they also reported with lower levels of stress.

The shift profile is not significant in perceived self-efficacy level among the respondents with a significant value of 0.658. Assuming a significant level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected because the significant value is greater than the significant level (0.05). This means that shift is not a determinant of perceived self-level. The present study was supported by the study of Central European Journal of Public Health (2018) in their article Assessment of work-related stress by using salivary cortisol level examination among early morning shift workers. Accordingly, early morning shifts have a negative effect on the hypothalamic-pituitary adrenal axis. Based on the results, irregular shift work has a greater increase in cortisol excretion after waking in the morning and a slower progressive recovery of the organism during the workday, in addition cortisol levels were significantly higher in older women than in older men but did not differ in younger subjects.

The number of seminars profile is not significant in perceived self-efficacy level among the respondents with a significant value of 0.331. Assuming a significant level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected because the significant value is greater than the significant level (0.05). This means that number of seminars is not a determinant of perceived self-level. This was contrast in the study of Guskey (1998) he found that the more teachers exposed to training, the more efficacious teachers tended to rate new method as more important. He also claimed that teachers with trainings felt greater responsibility for both positive and negative student learning and had more positive feelings toward teaching.

The length of service profile is not significant in perceived self-efficacy level among the respondents with a significant value of 0.816. Assuming a significant level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected because the significant value is greater than the significant level (0.05).

This means that length of service is not a determinant of perceived self-level. The result supported by the recent studies by Huberman's work, with Day and Gu (2007) they found that most teachers in mid-career (i.e., Years 8–23) experience increases in motivation and commitment, whereas increased proportions of teachers in the later stage of their career stage ranging 24 years of experience reported declining motivation.

Another study conducted by some authors of previous studies outside education has noted this decline in work motivation in the late-career stages.

The Number of learners is not significant in determining perceived self-efficacy level among respondents with a significant value of 0.561. Assuming a significant level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected because the significant value is greater than the significant level (0.05). This means that the number of learners is not a determinant of perceived self-level. Woolfolk (1998) explained that teacher with high self-efficacy can still accomplish the task successfully despite of large class at hand and on the other hand, failure displays a low level of self-efficacy.

Table 5 shows the absolute value of the computed Pearson r value of 0.493 is greater than or equal to 0.4 and less than or equal to 0.6 which indicates that stress level and perceived self-efficacy has moderately strong correlation. Meanwhile, assuming a significant level of 0.05, the significant value 0.012 is smaller than the significant level, thus it can be concluded that the null hypothesis is rejected. It means that the views or perceptions of the respondents are different when grouped according to specific profile. The Pearson r value is negative this means an inverse correlation as self-

efficacy goes up while stress goes down. The computed Pearson r Values is 0.493. That means there is significant correlation between stress level and perceived self-efficacy among the respondents. This means that teachers who were handling learners with special educational needs in Bagong Nayon II show high self-efficacy rather than experiencing stress.

The results of the study was supported by the study of Bandura (1997) accordingly, people with high self-efficacy are resilient and more motivational in challenging situations, the one with low self-efficacy can give up more easily and can lead to negative feelings such as stress, anxiety and these feelings may decrease the efficiency of individuals negatively or positively. Teachers with low self-efficacy levels experienced burnout. Another study of Bandura (1993) pointed out that people with high self-efficacy tend to have greater cognitive resourcefulness, strategic flexibility, and effectiveness in managing their environment, and set motivating goals for themselves.

Bandura (2002) Claimed that teachers with a high level of self-efficacy have a positive attitude towards everything. They always have control on their emotions, as a result they seldom display their anger in front of their students and this attitude assures high achievement. Teachers with high level of self-efficacy are open to new methods and have the ability to adopt new techniques.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings from the study, respondents were classified to be mostly middle-aged, single female teachers, with MA/MS units but without much training and work experience; Job rank is generally low and working the morning shift with 1 to 5 learners requiring special attention

Based on the findings from the study, specific demographics were identified to be more likely to experience stress than some, namely: male, single, with post-graduate units, and higher positioned respondents. On the other hand, Age, work shift, length of service, trainings and seminars attended and number of students with special requirement do not determine the stress level that respondents undergo.

Respondents belonging to the 36-40 years old age group were found to have the highest level of perceived self-efficacy. Other factors such as marital status, educational attainment, job rank, work shift, access to trainings and seminars, length of service and number of students with special needs were also identified as determinants of perceived self-efficacy, since single respondents, those with MA degrees, high-ranking personnel, those working the PM shift, those who were able to attend seminars, those more tenured and with more students with special requirements were found to have higher level of self-efficacy. On the other hand, gender was discovered to be not influential in determining self-efficacy, as both male and female are at similar levels.

The study shows that among the 9 classes in which the respondents were grouped, age, civil status, educational attainment, job rank, work shift, access to training and seminars, length of service and number of student with special requirements were found to have minimal influence in determining the respective stress levels of each respondent. On the other hand, the gender profile of the participants was discovered to have a huge impact on their stress level.

The study reveals that none of the identified profiles (age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, job rank, work shift, access to training and seminars, length of service and number of student with special requirements) are significantly influential to the respondent's perceived self-efficacy.

The study reveals that the views and perceptions of the participants can be influenced by means of grouping them according to specific profiles and that perceived self-efficacy and stress level have a moderately strong negative correlation; As the respondents' self-efficacy increases, their stress level decreases.

Based on the foregoing findings, the following further conclusions were drawn:

1. The purpose of this research study was to measure the level of stress and self-efficacy among the faculty of Bagong Nayon II National High School. The methodologies utilized were sufficient to obtain the data needed to support the researcher's proposition that the faculty in general have tolerable stress levels with high self-efficacy.
2. Respondents were classified to be mostly middle-aged, single female teachers, with MA/MS units but without much training and work experience; Job rank is generally low and working the morning shift with 1 to 5 learners requiring special attention.

3. There are specific demographics that are more likely to experience stress than some, namely: male, single, with post-graduate units, and higher positioned respondents. On the other hand, Age, work shift, length of service, trainings and seminars attended and number of students with special requirement do not determine the stress level that respondents undergo.

4. Some respondents have noticeably deviated from the research findings, particularly, the male participants with heightened stress levels and the more experienced teachers with low self-efficacy. To address these, stress management programs and perceived self-efficacy have been designed and proposed. These programs aim alleviate stress by 1) increasing the physical, mental emotional, social and hobbies of the respondents, 2) promoting perceived self-efficacy by 1. developing skills in effective student engagement. 2) Developing teachers on effective approaches on classroom management and 3) impart knowledge on current instructional strategies.

With these, the researcher looks to improve the overall morale in the school by reducing stress levels felt by the respondents and fostering self-efficacy.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the conclusions drawn from the study, the following are hereby recommended:

1. Teaching is one of the most stressful occupations, and teachers need to be supported through specific efforts. The school administrators must realize that stress is a serious issue which can affect teachers' ability to perform during their class. With this, programs must be established to render support among teachers focusing on decreasing their stress and ways to improve their self-efficacy should be highly considered.
2. Researchers should define accurately the requirements in choosing the respondents and increase the sample size enlisted to obtain more reliable findings for further studies.
3. The researcher should generalize findings across a certain area to increase coverage outside of one institution
4. To conduct study considering the timing of the survey; It is highly recommended to compare findings obtained from low-activity period versus those from peak seasons (examination week, grades and forms submission, etc.)
5. Teachers must pursue self-development and continuing education to update themselves on issues regarding stress management. Stress management provides a number of ways to manage anxiety and maintain overall well-being ("Stress", 2013).
6. To allow a longer time to observe the respondents before and after implementing programs proposed to measure its effectiveness.
7. Trainings and seminars on stress management must be conducted. Continuous Acknowledgement, praises and rewards must be given to teachers for their excellent performances and achievements which will help them enable to discover and maximize their true potentials and become more efficacious and stress free. Lastly the school administrators must provide the supervision needed by the teachers at all times.
8. Stress management is aimed primarily at male teachers.
9. Programs for Self-efficacy should aim primarily at older teachers.
10. The programs must be taken as a tool in enhancing teachers' self-efficacy and preventing stress.

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